

PP-110 : Strengthening the Supervision Mechanism of Medical Officer of Health Areas Under Regional Director of Health Services-Colombo

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BACKGROUND:

- Regular and comprehensive supervision of services delivered by Medical Officer of Health (MOH) Offices is crucial to ensure timeliness, accuracy and quality of service

DESCRIPTION OF THE INTERVENTION/ INITIATIVE:

- From 2025 all completed supervision reports were collected monthly from each MOH and evaluated at district level.

- At the end of each month;

- New formats for the ensuing month
- Evaluated supervisions from the previous month
- Official written communication acknowledging the number of supervision reports received. **(Figure 1)**

Were sent to MOH offices.

- MOH offices had access to view a database which identified each supervisory officer by name and designation with the number of supervisions submitted. **(Figure 2)**
- Progress of reporting was displayed at supervisory officers' meetings. Key observations were communicated duly via online meetings.

METHODS USED FOR THE EVALUATION:

- Medical officers and the public health nursing sister should complete **six** supervisions per month while supervising public health inspector and supervising public health midwife should complete **ten**.
- All supervision reports submitted on the last day of each month were considered timely
- Completeness was evaluated at district level.

RESULTS:

Figure 3: MOH performance in supervisions (January vs February 2025)

- In January 9 MOHs achieved a submission rate $\geq 50\%$ while 13 achieved $\geq 50\%$ in February.

LESSONS LEARNT:

- Transparent monitoring systems improve quality of supervisions and thus potentially improve overall performance of services delivered by MOH offices

Figure 1: Official written communication acknowledging the number of supervision reports

Figure 2: Supervision monitoring dashboard

Figure 4: Good practices of MOHs